

BIOVEXO

Biocontrol of Xylella and its vector in olive trees for integrated pest management

- BIOVEXO Highlights of 2024 - We Wish You A Wonderful Festive Season

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Addressing *Xylella fastidiosa* in Europe: A pathogen par Priorité

In 2013, the appearance of *Xylella fastidiosa* (Xf) was followed by an outbreak in Apulia in Olive, in southern Italy. Currently, this bacterium, regarded as one of Europe's most hazardous plant pathogens, is primarily associated with Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS), in Europe. The bacterium lives in the plant xylem tissue and is commonly spread by insect vectors feeding in the xylem. The bacterium leads to severe diseases in diverse crops, and ornamental and forest species, significantly impacting agriculture, gardens, and the environment, with substantial economic consequences.

Since the initial identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies *pauca* in Apulia, diverse subspecies have been detected in various European regions, including Corsica, mainland France, the Balearic Islands, mainland Spain, Portugal, central Italy (Tuscany) as well as in the Mediterranean countries, Lebanon and Israel.

A silent spreader

Deemed as a consequence of trade globalization and climate change, the pathogen was presumably introduced from the Americas. The ornamental plant trade has been proposed as the main pathway of Xf introduction and spread within Europe. A quiet and stealthy microorganism, it can be asymptomatic for years. Xf is categorized into five subspecies: *fastidiosa*, *pauca*, *multiplex*, *sandyi*, and *morus*. Subspecies *fastidiosa* and *pauca* have been extensively researched due to their economic impact on significant crops, particularly citrus and grapevine in South and North America, respectively.

Olives in trees and infected Olive trees by the dreaded *Xylella fastidiosa* © Shutterstock

The categorization of subspecies is somewhat connected to the variety of hosts they target, even though specific strains possess the capability to infect multiple hosts. Primarily, the signs of infection induced by different Xf strains manifest as necrosis at the leaf margins or scorching, resembling the symptoms seen in grapevines affected by Xf subsp. fastidiosa. However, symptoms induced by *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* are characterized by foliar wilt and interveinal chlorosis (areas of the leaf located between the veins exhibit a yellowing or loss of green color), while those caused by *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in certain hosts may display dense canopies and reduced fruit size. Moreover, Xf does not have an independent, free-living phase in its life cycle and has exclusively been identified in connection with its plant and insect hosts. 696 plant species have been reported as either naturally or artificially infected hosts, belonging to 88 botanic families (EFSA, 2023).

After Apulia, in 2016, the first strain of Xf was detected in Mallorca and within one year, 400 cases of infection have been reported from the Balearic islands. In the same year, November, the Xf subspecies *pauca* ST80 was related to olive decline and mortality in Ibiza.

Almond fields in Mallorca © Shutterstock

Xylella in the EU

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In Mallorca, in 2017, most of the 50 – 60 detected cases in olive trees in Mallorca belong to a subspecies of the Xf called multiplex, and to a strain that does not cause severe symptoms in this species. Thus, the efforts to eradicate it from this island are focused on almond trees, which are worse hit by the bacterium.

In 2017, understanding the urgency and havoc this bacterium can create for the future of plant life, the Spanish “El Mundo” newspaper has described Xylella as the “Ebola for olive trees”.

Xylella fastidiosa sub species pauca in 2024

The Xf subsp. pauca, which is responsible for causing citrus variegated chlorosis (CVC), is a regulated biological agent and is listed under the Agricultural Bioterrorism Protection Act in the USA.

Xf subspecies pauca, which is found to be responsible for citrus variegated chlorosis in Brazil, has been reasonably well-characterized in coffee and citrus plants. Later it was found to infect not only olive trees but also ornamental hibiscus (*Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*), plum (*Prunus domestica*). After its appearance in Mallorca at the beginning of this year, Xf pauca now continues to create havoc in Apulia, although the more efficient implementation of containment measures has greatly decreased its speed of spread.

As the pauca strain continues to be identified, infecting more and more new species across the Mediterranean region, ongoing genetic research is revealing crucial characteristics of the pathogen. Considering the pathogen’s unexpected appearance in locations where it was previously undetected (potentially due to its asymptomatic nature), research endeavors are actively working to enhance our comprehension of Xf’s intra and inter-subspecies evolution shedding light on the bacterium’s relationships with host range and geographic distribution.

Undoubtedly, it has been demonstrated that the bacterium exhibits adaptability to changes within and across hosts through the utilization of signaling systems.

“Living with the pathogen”

The detection of Xf subspecies pauca in Mallorca in 2023 did not come as a significant surprise to the community. Earlier research conducted in Corsica, France, had suggested that the Xf pathogen had likely been present for a longer duration than previously assumed. Similar observations were made in Mallorca, where a substantial mortality of almond trees was noted from around 2003 in the eastern part of the island, previously linked to fungal diseases. The probable introductions of subsp. fastidiosa and subsp. multiplex in Mallorca were traced back to approximately 1993, deduced from the reconstruction of the almond leaf scorch disease (ALSD) epidemic using evidence from epidemiology, dendrochronology, and molecular biology. Therefore, adopting preventive and phytosanitary measures is imperative, along with developing sound practices in soil management, fertilization, pruning, and irrigation. Simply uprooting trees would not eradicate the pathogen from the region. It is hypothesized that the risk of pathogen expansion to uninfected sites would escalate without effective control of all alternative host plants in OQDS-affected areas. Ultimately, an integrated strategy for controlling X. fastidiosa subsp. pauca should reflect the need for more inclusive governance and management of a quarantine plant pathogen affecting a vast area. Further research should focus on new strategies for managing X. fastidiosa subsp. pauca, including genetic research for resistance and vector control methods. However, the primary emphasis should be on enhancing treatment-focused studies to maintain plant productivity.

Xylella in the EU

The BIOVEXO project is exploring innovative biopesticides targeting the Xylella bacterium on olives. As of 2024, the project activities have undertaken various

trials of olive orchards in the study areas of Apulia (Italy), and Mallorca (Spain, Balearic Islands).

In the trial areas, with the purpose of containment of the Xylella, application of the sample biopesticides is via foliar spray by endotherapy (injection in the trunks) and irrigation by drips.

Dr. Pasquale Saldarelli, senior scientist at CNR, Italy who is closely involved in these trials remarks “Indeed we are currently conducting large-scale field trials, which are now midway through, and have obtained promising results from the selected biopesticides. Let’s await the completion of these trials to achieve conclusive answers regarding the

efficacy of the biopesticides in mitigating the diseases caused by this deadly Xylella bacterium.” His insights underscore the potential of biopesticides in combating this serious threat, offering hope for a future where sustainable agricultural practices can effectively manage and control plant diseases.

Stay tuned for more exciting updates on the groundbreaking BIOVEXO trials.

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Progress in Understanding *Xylella fastidiosa* Pauca ST53 in Mallorca: Implications for Biopesticide Development

Nearly a year after the first detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* pauca ST53 in Mallorca, researchers are continuing efforts to track and manage this highly destructive strain. This bacterial pathogen has already caused widespread devastation in southern Italy, where over 21 million olive trees have succumbed to infection over the last decade. In Mallorca, the strain remains localized, with cases concentrated in the Sencelles area, but concerns are rising about its potential to spread, particularly through the wild olive tree (acebuche), a species abundant across the Balearic Islands.

In response to this outbreak, the Balearic Government has partnered with the Valencian Institute for Agricultural Research and the Institute for Sustainable Agriculture of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). Their goal is to investigate the origin and scope of the ST53 strain and to evaluate how it interacts with other subspecies of *Xylella fastidiosa* that are already present on the island. Thus far, 114 wild olive trees, 34 cultivated olive trees, and 18 other plants from seven forest and ornamental species have tested positive for the bacteria, all within a relatively confined area of about one square kilometer.

Researchers are particularly concerned about the role of the wild olive tree in the spread of *Xylella fastidiosa*. This tree species, which is widespread throughout the Balearic Islands, could act as a reservoir for the bacteria, facilitating its transmission to other areas. Diego Olmo, from the Institute for Agrifood and Fisheries Research and Training of the Balearic Islands (IRFAP), has raised alarms that by 2029, we could see large sections of olive and wild olive trees in central Mallorca exhibiting severe symptoms, similar to what has already occurred in Italy.

Complicating the situation is the presence of multiple *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies on the island. In addition to the pauca ST53 strain, the subspecies multiplex ST1 and ST81 are also present, with ST81 particularly affecting wild olives. Co-infections between ST53 and ST81 have been detected, raising concerns about how these interactions

might impact the disease's progression and the effectiveness of control strategies. Given that all three subspecies share the same insect vector, *Philaenus spumarius*, there is an increased risk of genetic recombination, which could lead to new hybrid strains with unpredictable behavior.

A significant challenge to eradication efforts is the similarity between the symptoms caused by the different strains. Many wild olive trees infected with ST81 display symptoms that resemble those seen in the early stages of ST53 infection, complicating diagnosis and treatment. Olmo notes that the sheer number of infected wild olives in the area further complicates any plans to halt the spread of the disease.

The origin of the ST53 strain in Mallorca remains uncertain. Preliminary molecular analyses using sequence capture enrichment (ECS) suggest that the strain shares genomic similarities with those found in southern Italy and Costa Rica, indicating a potential common source. Ongoing research aims to further clarify the strain's host range, virulence, and timeline of introduction to the island.

Olmo emphasizes that these findings are critical for assessing the epidemiological implications of ST53's presence in Mallorca and for developing appropriate management strategies. With continued research, the team hopes to gain a clearer understanding of the strain's behavior, which will ultimately aid in the development of sustainable solutions, including biopesticides, to control the disease and protect the island's agricultural and natural ecosystems.

Olmo presented these findings at the XXI Congress of the Spanish Society of Phytopathology, held recently in Córdoba, underscoring the urgent need for coordinated efforts to combat this emerging threat.

Please follow this [LINK](#) to read the full article in Spanish.

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Harnessing the plant microbiome for sustainable crop production

BIOVEXO project partner AIT has published, in collaboration with international research partners, a pivotal article in 'Nature Reviews Microbiology' underscoring the transformative potential of the plant microbiome in fostering sustainable agriculture. This comprehensive review examines the intricate relationships between plants and microorganisms, offering fresh perspectives on how these interactions can be harnessed to enhance sustainable food systems. The findings described in this article also reflect the research of the BIOVEXO project, aiming to develop biopesticides that are eco-friendly whilst being effective in the protection of our crops.

Image: © Shutterstock

Challenges in Agriculture

Agriculture today faces multifaceted challenges as it grapples with the demands of a rapidly growing global population amid a deteriorating environmental landscape. The long-term overuse of chemical fertilizers and pesticides has not only degraded the quality of soils but has also led to significant biodiversity loss and contamination of water resources, thereby imperilling both food security and ecological integrity. Furthermore, as natural resources become increasingly scarce, the strain on agricultural systems intensifies, forcing reliance on unsustainable practices to meet production needs. In light of this, feeding an estimated 9 billion people by 2050 necessitates a paradigm shift toward regenerative, eco-friendly farming techniques that restore soil health, reduce chemical inputs, and promote resilience in food systems, ensuring both environmental sustainability and food security for future generations.

The Power of the Plant Microbiome

The plant microbiome, a diverse community of microorganisms including bacteria, fungi, archaea, and viruses, plays a crucial role in supporting plant health and growth. These microorganisms inhabit various parts of the plant, such as roots, leaves, and even flowers, forming distinct ecosystems both above and below ground. The most active microbial habitat is the rhizosphere, where root exudates and decaying organic matter create a nutrient-rich environment for microbial activity. In this ecosystem, microorganisms interact with plants by promoting growth, protecting against pathogens, and enhancing nutrient uptake. These beneficial interactions offer immense potential for natural pest control, as certain microbial species can act as biocontrol agents by suppressing harmful pathogens or pests. The ability of plants to selectively recruit these beneficial microbes through root exudates and other chemical signals further underscores their potential role in pest management, positioning the plant microbiome as a promising alternative to chemical pesticides.

Harnessing the potential of the plant microbiome to develop biological pesticides has become a focal point of research. Scientists aim to identify and isolate specific microbial strains that can combat pests or inhibit plant pathogens. By understanding the complex interactions within the microbiome, researchers are developing biopesticides—natural compounds derived from microorganisms—that can target pests without harming the environment. This approach has the added benefit of

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reducing chemical input in agriculture, addressing concerns related to soil degradation, biodiversity loss, and pollution. Research efforts, such as those undertaken by the BIOVEXO project, are working toward creating biocontrol solutions tailored to agricultural needs, particularly in combating devastating plant diseases like *Xylella fastidiosa*. Through careful field trials and microbial formulation, scientists are moving closer to providing farmers with sustainable and effective pest management tools, advancing agricultural resilience in the face of growing environmental pressures.

"Our goal is to fully harness the potential of the plant microbiome to make agriculture more sustainable and resilient."

Dr. Stéphane Compant
BIOVEXO - Scientific Coordinator

Meeting the future demand for food production in light of a growing global population is a significant challenge, especially with the need to reduce the environmental impact of agricultural practices. Sustainable solutions, such as biofertilizers, biopesticides, and biostimulants, are increasingly seen as critical alternatives. Examples like nitrogen-fixing *Bradyrhizobium* inoculants in soybean production, which reduce the need for chemical fertilizers and cut greenhouse gas emissions, highlight the success of these approaches. Microbial products based on strains such as *Trichoderma* and *Bacillus* also provide effective plant protection, showcasing the potential of microbial applications in promoting sustainable agriculture. Despite these achievements, challenges remain, such as inconsistent field results and a need for greater understanding of microbiome interactions to improve product performance in natural environments.

The Path Ahead

BIOVEXO and other researchers are working to overcome these limitations through approaches like designing microbial consortia and exploring microbiome modulation. Improved understanding of plant-microbe interactions,

particularly in relation to different plant varieties, could lead to enhanced crop production and support more sustainable practices. However, gaps in microbiome data and the need for better data management persist. A coordinated effort is essential to advance the field, alongside considerations for product safety and environmental impact.

Find out More

If you are interested to read the full article, follow this [LINK](#) to the peer-reviewed review journal *Nature Reviews Microbiology* and find out more about:

- Plant microbiome functions and mechanisms,
- Strategies to improve abiotic plant stress tolerance and plant nutrition,
- Current microbial applications,
- Microbial biofertilizers,
- Biostimulants,
- Applications for biofortification,
- Upcoming plant microbiome applications,
- Strain improvement,
- Synthetic communities,
- Soil transplantation and rewilding of plant microbiomes,
- Microbiome modulation,
- Plant breeding for beneficial plant-microbe interactions,
- Digital tools,
- New application areas.

You are also invited to explore the BIOVEXO website and get more insights on the progress of BIOVEXO's research, field trials and other activities: www.biovexo.eu.

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A new study indicates presence of natural traits of resistance to *Xylella fastidiosa* in Leccino offspring

The recent publication 'A survey in natural olive resources exposed to high inoculum pressure indicates the presence of traits of resistance to *Xylella fastidiosa* in Leccino offspring' highlights the progress made in fighting *Xylella fastidiosa*. BIOVEXO partner Mr. Pasquale Saldarelli from CNR, co-author of this publication, contributed with his research significantly to this publication – this is a must read if you are concerned about the spread of *Xylella* and the health of olive trees.

Graphic: RTDS

Background to modern farming practices

The cultivated olive (*Olea europaea*, subsp. *europaea*, var. *europaea*) is a vital crop, especially in the Mediterranean Basin, which accounts for 95% of global olive oil production. The olive tree represents a rich genetic diversity, with over 1,200 recognized cultivars and thousands of minor ones. However, modern, intensive farming practices are narrowing this biodiversity, with fewer traditional varieties used in new cultivation methods. These traditional varieties, which have been selected and tested over centuries by local farmers for their resilience to climate change and lower resource requirements, are crucial for sustainable olive farming. Unfortunately, this biodiversity is often underexplored, as seen in regions like Apulia, where local varieties have been grafted with more commercially viable cultivars, reducing genetic diversity.

The greatest threat to olives: *Xylella*

One of the most significant threats to olive trees today is the *Xylella fastidiosa* bacterium, which causes the olive quick decline syndrome (OQDS). This disease was first discovered in southern Italy in 2013 and has since caused severe epidemics, devastating millions of olive trees, including centuries-old specimens. The bacterium, spread by the spittlebug (*Philaeus spumarius*), has found ideal conditions in the Mediterranean climate, leading to large-scale outbreaks in the Apulia region, where susceptible cultivars like Cellina di Nardò and Ogliarola salentina are predominant. However, isolates of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies *pauca* have also been detected in South America, specifically in Brazil and Argentina, associated to similar symptoms in olives. In contrast, California has reported only mild symptoms in olive trees, due to the presence of a different *Xylella* subspecies.

At present, no curative treatments exist for *Xylella*-infected plants. Current control measures focus on reducing insect vector populations and removing infected trees, though these strategies are only effective if implemented promptly. A promising long-term approach is the use of genetic resistance, as seen in other *Xylella*-susceptible crops like grapes and citrus. In these crops, certain genotypes demonstrate natural resistance to the bacterium, offering a path forward for breeding resistant varieties. For example, some wild relatives of the domesticated grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) and specific citrus varieties exhibit strong resistance to *Xylella* infection, and this resistance has been linked to specific genetic loci, such as the PdR1 locus in grapevines.

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Signs for optimism

In olives, two cultivars, Leccino and FS-17, have demonstrated a degree of resistance to Xylella. Trees of these varieties show lower bacterial loads and fewer symptoms compared to other cultivars. Research suggests that these resistant cultivars are able to control the replication of the bacterium in xylem vessels and manage drought stress more effectively. However, despite the rich genetic diversity within the olive germplasm, large-scale screenings for resistance have not yet identified any cultivars with higher resistance than Leccino and FS-17. This highlights the difficulties in conducting olive breeding programs, which face challenges due to the long time required for the selection of resistant genotypes.

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Recognizing the urgency of the situation, researchers have conducted extensive surveys in the Apulia region, which has been under high Xylella pressure for years. These surveys, conducted over six years, identified 171 spontaneous olive genotypes that showed no visible symptoms of Xylella infection. Over time, some genotypes did develop symptoms and were excluded from further research, but many remained asymptomatic or exhibited only mild symptoms. The parentage of these resistant genotypes was analysed to determine which cultivars contributed to their resilience. A few promising genotypes underwent more in-depth studies, including

transcriptomic profiling and controlled artificial bacterial inoculations to better understand their resistance mechanisms.

This work is part of broader research Italian (REACH-XY, RESIXO) and European (BeXyl) efforts, such as the BIOVEXO project, which has contributed significantly to understanding and combating Xylella infections in olives and other crops. BIOVEXO focuses on developing sustainable, bio-based pesticides to address the Xylella problem. As research continues, the identification of resistant genotypes and the development of effective biopesticides will be key to managing Xylella outbreaks and ensuring the long-term sustainability of olive cultivation.

To access the article, please follow this

[LINK](#)

If you wish to find out more about the work of the BIOVEXO project we welcome you to explore our website

[HERE](#)

Events & Activities

BIOVEXO goes Porto!

The BIOVEXO project partnership was in Porto, Portugal from 22nd January to 26th January 2024 for a highly-productive week of meetings and events! Here's a concise summary of our trip where we delved into project progress and outlined exciting plans for the year 2024

We began with our annual consortium meeting, held in the excellent REAL Restaurant. This was split over days 1 and 3. In our consortium meeting, we meticulously reviewed the strides made in our ongoing project.

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Here are the key takeaways

We dissected the achievements of the past year, celebrating milestones and acknowledging areas where we excelled. Metrics were scrutinized, and we celebrated the successful completion of critical deliverables. Our collective efforts (literally) bore fruit as Mallorca saw record olive harvests this year! In our field trials we witnessed tangible progress.

Candid discussions also ensued about the hurdles we encountered, for example, last summer's drought, which severely affected our trials in some locations. These challenges, though formidable, served as valuable learning opportunities. We identified bottlenecks, refined processes, and committed to continuous improvement.

Strategic Vision for 2024

With renewed vigor, we charted our course for the remaining 15 months of the BIOVEXO project. Our over-

arching goal: maximizing impact. In the project's final reporting period we look forward to a number of scientific publications.

Each Work Package aligned their objectives with the project-wide vision. Clear KPIs and KERs were established, ensuring that every action contributes to the larger research and innovation goals.

We emphasized the importance of agility—being responsive to shifts in the situation of Xylella as well as variations in weather.

Annual Plan Creation

Armed with insights from the past year, we crafted a robust annual plan for 2024, finalizing our field trials. This blueprint will guide us through the year, providing clarity and accountability.

Concrete goals were set, and we committed to periodic progress checks. Adjustments will be made as needed to keep us on track.

Team Unity and Collaboration

But our meeting wasn't just about data and strategies; it was a reaffirmation of our collective purpose. As we sipped coffee and exchanged ideas, we felt the pulse of a cohesive team—one that thrives on collaboration and one shared aspiration: to defeat Xylella.

In conclusion, our consortium meeting was more than a mere discussion; it was a compass pointing us toward a successful year ahead.

But, the BIOVEXO consortium meeting was not our only reason to visit Portugal: on 23rd January we met with experts from 4 other EU/EFSA-funded research projects in our Multi-Project Stakeholder Meeting.

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Strategic Vision for 2024

The Multi-Project Stakeholder Meeting was envisioned as a melting pot for scientific minds, where the [BIOVEXO](#) consortium were joined by experts from the [OLEAF4VALUE](#), [NOVATERRA](#), [BeXyl](#), and [Xvectors](#) projects. Here's a glimpse into the vibrant discussions that unfolded. We were hosted by the wonderful [Douro Museum](#), located in the fully-restored and adapted Casa da Companhia Velha, a building that is emblematic of the history of the world's oldest demarcated and regulated wine region at the heart of a World Heritage region.

Representatives from the 4 EU-funded research initiatives gathered with a common goal: sharing their respective approaches to: combatting [Xylella fastidiosa](#) – a bacterium that continues to pose threats to Europe's olive and almond trees in particular; reducing the use of pesticides in the Mediterranean region; valorisation of the olive leaf biomass by extracting novel bioactive compounds.

The room buzzed with anticipation as experts from diverse backgrounds exchanged ideas.

Project Progress and Insights

BIOVEXO began by outlining their work on biopesticides. Scientific Coordinator Stéphane Compant explained how the six candidate biocontrol solutions targeting both Xylella and its vector, the [spittlebug](#) have been refined and how the most promising solutions up-scaled for further testing.

The BeXyl project, led by [Blanca B. Landa](#), gave their

presentation remotely. This multidisciplinary project explores innovative solutions to manage Xylella outbreaks. Their approach encompasses prevention, rapid detection, search for resistance and outbreak management.

[OLEAF4VALUE](#), with its focus on valorizing olive biomass, shared insights on sustainable biorefining. Their cross-sectoral connections bridged the primary sector, technology providers, and sensor technology research.

[NOVATERRA](#), committed to underused biomass, showcased their consortium's efforts. Their holistic approach spanned raw material, biorefining, market validation, and sustainability assessment.

Finally, the Portuguese-based, EFSA-funded XVectors project was presented.

SoGrape Head of R&D, António Graça, and Head of Viticulture, José Manso, talking to the BIOVEXO consortium members

Advancements in Research

The Multi-project Stakeholder Meeting unveiled exciting developments and emphasized the tangible results that EU-funded research was delivering against major threats. Collaboration remained the guiding star. The potential for sharing information, holding joint-events and collaborating on communication activities was underscored. Preparedness and early detection emerged as key tools in the fight against Xylella. The stakes were high,

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given the economic and environmental heritage at risk. This convergence isn't just about research; it is about safeguarding Europe's green legacy!

Following the fascinating discussions, the BIOVEXO consortium was delighted to take to opportunity to travel to the nearby vineyards of NOVATERRA project partner SoGrape. There we were treated to an expert-guided vineyard tour, hosted by SoGrape Head of R&D, António Graça, and Head of Viticulture, José Manso. The Quinta do Seixo vineyard features the breath-taking landscape of the Douro Valley at a particular special place where the landscape mosaic provides a comprehensive example of agricultural landscape management through biodiversity conservation. It also features an array of solutions for slope vineyard systematization providing the best possible land use while minimizing soil erosion, landslide risk and water conservation. The BIOVEXO partners were beguiled by explanations of some of the ways in which technology is being used to track plant health.

In many aspects, Quinta do Seixo has been a test-bed for advanced sustainable farming techniques for mountain viticulture. Many different projects have been developed and implemented at Quinta do Seixo:

- Centimetric resolution slope mapping to evaluate surface and subsurface water flow in support of intelligent drainage systems and mitigating erosion and landslide risk
- Locally dedicated weather station integrating a vast European network – cooperation with KNMI / Copernicus / WMO for E-OBS dataset
- Functional biodiversity through conservation farming – project LIFE+ BIODIVINE, Syngenta's Operation Pollinator
- Mating disruption against the grapevine moth (*Lobesia botrana*) in slope vineyards
- Conservation of grapevine's intra-varietal diversity and development of polyclonal selection
- Cover crop management in rain-fed vineyards
- Low-cost fruit maturity optoelectronic sensor – patent registered

- Agricultural robotics

The BIOVEXO team was extremely grateful to our hosts at the Quinta do Seixo vineyard!

On days 3 and 4 of our trip to Portugal we were back in Porto, where we concluded our Consortium Meeting and held our Project Review Meeting with the European Commission.

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On the final day we enjoyed a brief walk to the river in Porto before holding a debriefing meeting. All in all, it was a hugely successful trip. All the BIOVEXO partners learned a lot and great plans were set in place for the coming year to ensure that our research will continue to produce outcomes that will move us towards our goal of defeating Xylella. Let's continue this journey together, fuelled by determination and a shared commitment to excellence!

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BIOVEXO at the IPM Conference 2024 in Brussels

The BIOVEXO team, featuring members from the coordinators RTDS Association and the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, recently represented the project at the IPM Conference 2024, titled “Holistic IPM: Reducing Pesticide Use.” This conference, held on 14th May in Brussels was organized by the IPM Decisions and IPMWorks, and marked the conclusion of the both Horizon 2020 sister projects.

This day-long conference at the popular Herman Teirlinck building, in the heart of Brussels, attracted over 130 attendees from around 15 European countries, including representatives from various agricultural, plant health, and pest management organizations, research institutes, and industry actors.

The BIOVEXO project generated a lot of interest at this event, with participants from the IPM community keen to know more about its foreseen biological solutions for combating the deadly pathogen *Xylella fastidiosa* in Europe with advanced integrated pest management (IPM) strategies for important food trees like Olives and Almonds. A BIOVEXO promotional poster along with project flyers was showcased and distributed at this event.

[Click here](#) to check out Dr. Günter Brader’s (representative from the Scientific Coordination, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology) message at the conference.

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Innovation in plant protection

The conference was opened by Diego Canga Fano, Director of Quality Policy, Research & Innovation, and Outreach of the European Commission’s Directorate for Agriculture (DG AGRI). In his speech, Canga highlighted, innovating

plant protection in Europe. He emphasized the significance of Horizon Europe initiatives working towards reducing reliance on harmful chemical pesticides and fostering the development of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies that are both economically viable and environmentally sustainable.

Nick Paveley, ADAS / © RTDS

IPM in action

Nick Paveley and Mark Ramsden from ADAS, a member of the project coordination of IPM Decisions, summarized the main outcomes of the IPM Decisions project. This was followed by an engaging presentation on scientific evidence of pest regulation through landscape diversity by Dr Sandrine Petit, from INRAE, France. She spoke about how ecological intensification of agriculture (EIA) aims to assure food security by harnessing ecosystem services. Available modeling tools and approaches to forecasting natural pest control were diverse and promising, but the integration of accurate descriptions of farming practices at the landscape scale remains a challenge. According to Petit, few studies integrated socio-economic aspects and provided approaches to guide and co-design the transition to future agroecological landscapes.

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Further into the event, speaking on quantifying the potential of reducing pesticides, Prof. Titto Catiff (Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore), spoke on the framework for the implementation of IPM, based on the decision-making process, which involves four kinds of decisions.

- Strategic
- tactical on whether and when
- on which control measures to be adopted
- operational decisions.

Each type of decision plays a critical role in ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of the IPM program. Strategic decisions are long-term and focus on the overall goals and direction of the pest management program. These decisions set the framework within which all other decisions are made. They often involve goal setting, policy development, resource allocation, research and development including risk management.

Sandrine Petit, INRAE / © RTDS

Tactical decisions are medium-term and focus on planning and scheduling activities to achieve strategic goals. These decisions involve determining whether and when to implement specific control measures. They include pest monitoring, intervention intervals, selection of control measures, etc.

The decisions on “which control measures to adopt” involve selecting specific pest control methods that will be

used to manage pest populations. The choice of control measures is critical and is based on the following considerations. Effectiveness, environmental impact, economic viability, compatibility of control measures with other IPM strategies and agricultural practices, and long-term sustainability of such control measures.

Operational decisions are short-term and involve the day-to-day implementation of pest control measures. These decisions ensure that the chosen control strategies are executed effectively and efficiently. They include the application of control measures, continuously evaluating the effectiveness of control measures, and adjusting as required to improve results.

In an effective IPM program, these four types of decisions are interconnected and inform one another. This integrated approach ensures that pest management is sustainable, environmentally responsible, and economically viable.

Titto Catiff, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Italy / © RTDS

Importance of decision support systems

Emphasizing the role of decision support systems (DSS), Dr. Stefane Carlesi (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna) presented the effectiveness of rock powder for olive-fly control. The olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) is the most serious pest for olives. The larvae (maggots) of the olive fruit fly feed inside the fruit, destroying the pulp and

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allowing the entry of secondary bacteria and fungi that lead to the rotting of the fruit. Feeding damage can cause premature fruit drops and reduce fruit quality for both table olive and olive oil production.

Stefan Carlesi Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna / © RTDS

Carlesi mentioned that pest control might not be only non-chemical but highly DSS (decision support system). According to him, a healthy crop has reduced pesticide use and impact, a safer environment, enhanced biodiversity, avoidance of resistance, and better pest control. Moreover, he spoke about the 5 pillars of holistic IPM.

1. Agricultural landscapes with diverse semi-natural habitats
2. Cropping system designed to decrease.
3. Preferential use of non-chemical control options
4. Optimized decision-making to avoid unnecessary treatments.
5. Increased efficiency of treatments

This presentation was particularly relevant to the BIOVEXO project as it focused on pests affecting olive orchards in Italy. While the BIOVEXO project targets the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*, the olive fly, a parasite of olives, although dreadful, poses a significantly lower threat than *Xylella*.

After the coffee break, the session continued with the topic of holistic weed management strategy in arable farming by Johan Devriendt. Devriendt is a farmer from Jura in the Flemish part of Belgium and maintains a farmland along with his family. He shared his personal experiences on weed management and how his farm is adapting to welcoming diverse crops. He also emphasized that good IPM strategies are required for crop health as well as for the health of his farm and family.

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Evidence of IPM cost efficiency: results from our network

Dr. Mette Sønderskov, from Aarhus University, presented the most discussed and debated topic on the cost-effectiveness of IPM. Sønderskov discussed the methods of biocontrol measures like using bait with hormones, chemotropic/biological attraction, mating disruption or mating confusion, and enhancement of natural regulation. Biopesticides, derived from natural materials such as animals, plants, bacteria, and certain minerals, offer a cost-effective alternative to conventional chemical pesticides. Their cost-effectiveness arises from several factors: reduced development and registration costs, minimal environmental impact, and the potential for sustainable pest management. As biopesticides are typically less harmful to beneficial insects and ecosystems, they can decrease the long-term costs associated with environmental cleanup and health care. Additionally, their use can mitigate the development of pest resistance, ensuring long-term efficacy and reducing the economic burden on agricultural systems.

Events & Activities

Thus, the integration of biopesticides into pest management programs can enhance both economic and environmental sustainability.

Mette Sønderskov on cost-effective IPM / © RTDS

IPM Demo Hubs

In the Peer-to-Peer learning session, Laure Triste and her team from IPM Works presented stories of creating Demo Hubs for farmer groups within the project. Her presentation emphasized how important it is to first get to know the farmers, create a safe space for them to interact and foster dialogue, and for frequent communications and joint agenda development. Speaking on the key role of a Hub Coach, Triste emphasized providing individual advice, organizing demo events for the wider public, facilitating the hub as a group, also connecting the hub internationally.

Speaking of the importance of Demo Hubs, Triste Laure informed that it is very important to show that IPM strategies work on the ground, for which the following points need to be checked.

- Relate to potential motivations for farmers to adopt IPM practices (technical, Economic, Market, Regulation)
- Adapt the topic and location for the audience.

- Take into account the farming calendar (seasons).
- Show success stories and challenges.
- Facilitate interaction and reflection.

[Click here](#) to watch Laure's video clip of the presentation at the IPM Conference 2024

IPM Workshop

After the lunch break, there was a series of workshops for the participants to choose from. SAGROPIA attended the "Biological Control in Integrated Pest Management" workshop.

The workshop was conducted by Karel Bolkmans, from the BioFirst group, and also featured experiences on IPM in private farms from the Belgian farmer and vine grower Christian Balduyck of the Glabais vineyard in the Walloon Brabant province in Belgium.

Discussing biocontrol-based IPM, Bolkmans said that prevention, monitoring, and suppression are the three important points. Biological control, or biocontrol, is a vital component of integrated pest management (IPM) strategies that aim to manage pest populations using natural enemies. The growing concern over pesticide resistance, pesticide residue, and the environmental impact of chemical controls has led to increased interest in biocontrol methods. In the workshop, the different types of biocontrol and their benefits were explored briefly:

- **Classical Biological control:** Introduction of ecologically adapted natural enemies from the area of origin.
- **Conservative Biological Control** and Conservation of natural enemies in the agroecosystem by using cultural practices or habitat management to enhance their activities and by eliminating non-selective pesticide sprays.
- **Augmentative biological control** involves the release of mass-reared natural enemies to manage pest populations.

Events & Activities

There are two primary methods:

1. **Seasonal Inoculative Biological Control:** Natural enemies are released periodically to establish a population that controls pests over a season.
2. **Inundative Biological Control:** Large numbers of natural enemies are released to quickly reduce pest populations.

The main benefits of biological control are:

- **Reduction in Pesticide Use:** By utilizing biological control, the reliance on chemical pesticides is significantly reduced.
- **Pesticide Resistance:** Biological control helps mitigate issues related to pests developing resistance to chemical pesticides.
- **Pesticide Reregistration and Residue Requirements:** Using biological control can simplify compliance with pesticide reregistration and reduce concerns about chemical residues on crops.

Proven Effectiveness and Affordability of Biocontrol-Based IPM

The workshop participants agreed that the effectiveness of biocontrol methods has been well-documented. Advanced large-scale production technologies have made biocontrol affordable for use in row crops, making it a viable option for many agricultural practices. However, workshop participants stated that the availability of modern biopesticides is limited for European farmers compared to other regions, due to very slow registration processes.

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) that incorporates biocontrol strategies offers proven effectiveness and affordability, particularly for row crops due to advanced production technologies. The benefits of biocontrol outlined were:

- **Proven Effectiveness:** Numerous studies have demonstrated the successful implementation of biocontrol in managing pest populations.
- **Affordability:** Large-scale production technologies make biocontrol solutions cost-effective for farmers.

- **Regulatory Challenges:** However, the availability of modern biopesticides remains limited for European farmers compared to other regions, primarily due to the slow registration process.

Biocontrol as a suitable alternative to traditional chemical pesticides

The workshop concluded that biocontrol methods, including classical, conservative, and augmentative biological control, offer sustainable, effective, and environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional chemical pesticides. These strategies not only help reduce pesticide use and mitigate resistance but also support biodiversity and ecosystem health. As regulatory processes evolve and more biocontrol products become available, the adoption of biocontrol-based IPM will continue to grow, benefiting farmers and the environment alike.

Takeaways from the IPM conference

In his closing remarks, Urban Hrovatič, Advisor at SE Europe Advisory Service Network, emphasized the importance of a holistic Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategy. He highlighted that the innovation chain in IPM must remain unbroken and that IPM is a comprehensive approach to pest control, combining various strategies and practices to grow healthy crops while minimizing pesticide use. The IPM Decisions and IPM Works projects have set a valuable precedent for advancing IPM strategies and future initiatives.

The conference provided BIOVEXO with valuable insights on IPM strategies. In response to the rising *Xylella* outbreaks in Europe, the BIOVEXO Project is developing innovative biopesticides targeting the *Xylella* bacterium. The carrier vector of *Xylella* is the meadow spittlebug (*Philaenus spumarius* L.) is a prolific pest in Europe. Conducting field trials in severely affected orchards of olives and almonds in Apulia Alicante and Mallorca, the project has yielded significant results with strategies for biological solutions. With one year remaining, BIOVEXO is gaining recognition and attracting interest due to the threat posed by the pathogen and the critical nature of its contribution to combating *Xylella*.

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Initiatives & Cooperations

BIOVEXO Joins the NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum

The BIOVEXO project is thrilled to join the NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum, an initiative brought to life by the SmartAgroHub consortium. This forum offers a crucial platform for collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and awareness-raising around the adoption of integrated pest management and biopesticides practices. By engaging in this initiative, BIOVEXO aims to highlight the importance of eco-friendly, bio-based solutions in agriculture, particularly in controlling devastating diseases like *Xylella fastidiosa*, which affects olive and almond orchards in Mediterranean regions.

From vision to opportunities

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The focus of the NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum endeavour is to increase capabilities to control the most “difficult-to-manage” pests and pathogens in fruits and vegetables. The BIOVEXO project team sees the NextGenBioPest Forum as an opportunity to not only share the latest findings from BIOVEXO’s ongoing research but also to foster dialogue between key stakeholders such as farmers, researchers, policymakers, and the agri-tech industry. This collaborative effort will help accelerate the adoption of sustainable pest management practices, reducing reliance on chemical pesticides and promoting more resilient agricultural systems. Through this forum, BIOVEXO hopes to raise awareness about the benefits of biological solutions and contribute to a broader movement towards sustainability in agriculture, ensuring healthier crops and ecosystems for future generations.

Bringing the Forum to life: The SmartAgroHub Consortium

The SmartAgroHub is an innovative competence center, spearheaded by the Agricultural University of Athens alongside 12 leading Greek companies, aimed at transforming agriculture through cutting-edge digital solutions. The consortium seeks to revolutionize agricultural practices by driving the sector’s digital transformation while promoting sustainability across the agri-food supply chain. Key areas of SmartAgroHub’s activities include intelligent agriculture, the development of sustainable solutions for increasing yields, and reducing environmental impact. By leveraging biosensors, digital technologies, and precision farming techniques, the consortium empowers farmers to optimize production while minimizing resource use.

In addition, SmartAgroHub focuses on environmental footprint assessments, sustainable product development, and fostering circular economy principles in agriculture. The initiative also supports research and development in biotechnology, novel foods, and energy-saving practices, contributing to the broader goal of advancing both productivity and environmental responsibility in agriculture.

NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum

This collaborative initiative will foster dialogue and innovation as the NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum will bring together experts, researchers, and stakeholders to explore sustainable pest management solutions. BIOVEXO actively participates in this forum, reflecting its commitment to raising awareness and advancing bio-

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based agricultural practices. This initiative creates a promising platform for sharing research and best practices in biological pest control, contributing to the ongoing development of sustainable agricultural systems. The forum provides a critical space for knowledge sharing, offering a chance for various stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, and farmers, to come together and discuss the latest advancements in biopesticides in workshops and many other collaborative formats. By facilitating such knowledge exchange, the forum

contributes to the wider adoption of eco-friendly solutions, driving the agricultural sector towards greater sustainability and resilience.

To find out more about the NextGenBioPest Stakeholder Forum and the SmartAgroHub, please visit the website here:

To Watch Out For

Upcoming conferences, workshops, and other events related to biocontrol of Xylella and integrated pest management

- **NextGenBioPest Initiative Workshop**

This workshop will facilitate an online discussion with experts from several EU-funded projects on the future of new methods for pest and pathogen control to safeguard human health and meet the challenge of increasing crop yields, while reducing the use of chemical pesticides. Watch out for news on this workshop taking place in the first quarter of 2025!

- **BIOVEXO Cluster Event**

A collaborative workshop with sister projects on the status of the fight against Xylella fastidiosa and innovative methods to control the pathogen. Watch out for news on this workshop taking place in the second quarter of 2025!

- **BIOVEXO Final Conference**

The BIOVEXO project will conclude with a final conference this autumn. The event will showcase groundbreaking research on Xylella fastidiosa, including advanced detection methods, vector control strategies, and host plant resistance. Watch out for news on this workshop taking place in the fourth quarter of 2025!

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Related Projects

Selection of EU-funded Projects

National Xylella projects & resources

Non Xylella-specific projects & resources

Project Partners

